

A New KURV in an Old Category

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Abstract: To compete with Black and Decker's Dustbuster, Dirt Devil's designer line of cordless vacuums uses style to evoke emotion. This moves the device from under the sink or in the basement to the front entry or family room. Dirt Devil changed the rules of the cordless vacuum marketplace by creating a new niche. They combined smart engineering design with elegant industrial design to invite customers to buy cordless vacuum for rooms they never would have put a cordless vacuum in before. Even the names are iconic and cute—KURV, KONE, KRUZ, BRUM, and KWIK. Dirt Devil claims it is "The New Shape of Clean."

Key words: *cordless vacuum, appliance*

The lowly Dustbuster was invented over 30 years ago. A remarkable product at the time, it created an entirely new market category for Black & Decker. Over a million of the rechargeable, cordless handheld vacuums were sold in the first year [1]. Moms used them to scoop up Cheerios that missed Junior's mouth; pet-owners used them to catch those fluffy wisps of hair that gather in nooks and crannies; weekend handymen used them to vacuum up the sawdust left by the latest project; and nearly everyone used them to pick up the dirt tracked in by the kids and dog. Although their competitors flooded the market with imitations, Black & Decker controlled 85% of the cordless market in 1985. After 100 million Dustbusters had been sold, the Smithsonian Institute acquired an original model in 1995. By 2004, Black & Decker had sold an estimated 150 million units [1]. Today Black & Decker has cyclonic Dustbusters, HEPA filter Dustbusters, wet/dry Dustbusters, and even Dustbusters that sport the emblems of eight southeastern universities, all in the mold of the original, very recognizable Dustbuster.

But where do most of these Dustbusters reside in a typical home? In my house, one is hidden in a cabinet under the kitchen sink, though I should probably add another one at the basement workbench and yet another in the garage. Of course, I rarely use my Dustbuster because the kitchen sink is not very close to the back door in my house where the dog and kids track everything imaginable into the house. I have an outlet near the back door, but I am not enthused about a Dustbuster hanging on the wall next to the lovely picture we bought on our last trip to France, even if the Dustbuster is a sleek platinum series model or sports the logo my alma mater. And I certainly don't want a Dustbuster mounted on the wall below the Dali print at the front entry of my home.

So what's a competitor to do? Answer—use design to change the competitive landscape. That is just what Dirt Devil did. Now Dirt Devil does not come from a recent lineage of high design. The company is a division of TTI Floor Care North America, which also owns the Hoover, Regina, and Royal floor cleaner lines. Some of their current upright vacuum cleaner models look like they might have been designed in the 1930's by

Raymond Loewy (who, by the way, designed the Hoover Company logo that is still in use today) with a shiny cast aluminum vacuum floor nozzle and an external cloth bag that inflates during operation. Others look like the Hoover vacuum cleaner I remember my mother using when I was a kid, except with brighter and shinier plastic instead of the dull gray or beige ABS plastic used 30 years ago. Still others build on the post-modern Dyson bagless cyclone vacuum cleaner style, which create a powerful vacuum action, but, much like the Pompidou Center in Paris, puts the insides on the outside. And the little red Dirt Devil corded handheld vacuum with the inflating cloth bag is iconic only because it has been around such a long time. Based on their product line, Dirt Devil would not be the first company that would come to mind to create a modern design icon.

Nevertheless, Dirt Devil contacted Karim Rashid, a prolific designer who claims that "every business should be completely concerned with beauty - it is after all a collective human need." [2]. Markus Allemann of Dirt Devil explains that "Form and function with appeal on the retailer shelf, a high level of product differentiation, and some emerging home trends were combined with the simple need to have a hand vac in easy reach. Karim had been approached and was willing to cooperate with us on the design."

What Rashid and Dirt Devil engineers created is a rechargeable, cordless handheld vacuum cleaner called the KURV with a simple, elegant shape reminiscent of an ancient brass urn. "Like furniture or other artifacts, we should have objects that we use for cleaning in our visible space to celebrate and enjoy, instead of putting them in the closet," says Rashid [3]. The shape is smooth and graceful, as shown in Figure 1. The metallic fleck in the muted but rich colors adds to the KURV's elegant look. The only ornamental design detail on the KURV is a simple band of peanut-shaped holes around the circumference at its widest diameter. The only hint that this is not a decorator accent for a room is the small, but very recognizable, Dirt Devil logo.

Figure.1 The high-style KURV need not be hidden in a closet or under the counter and is available in four designer colors. (Images courtesy of Royal Appliance Manufacturing Company; used with permission.)

The real delight of the KURV comes in using it. What looks like a decorative accent piece in the previously empty corner of the entry foyer becomes a handheld vacuum to suction up the dirt, leaves, and grime that gets tracked in at the front door. The handheld portion of the vacuum lifts smoothly out its base, as if by magic becoming a tool for cleaning up. The vacuum is activated by a button cleverly hidden in plain sight at the top end of the device. The suction end has a quarter-sized hole at a sharp angle to allow easy access to corners and

in narrow spaces. The KURV is not for big messes--it simply provides a satisfying 30-second quick clean-up without having to go to the broom closet or basement to retrieve the Dustbuster or, worse yet, the upright Hoover. In fact, it is such an appealing device that the kids are tempted to use it to clean up their own messes! Returning the KURV to its base is equally satisfying. The vacuum simply glides back into its base with unseen guides and gravity rotating vacuum to naturally seat it in position for recharging. A subtle charging light, not even visible when unplugged, comes on above the Dirt Devil logo, the only reminder that this is a handheld vacuum, not a decorative accent.

Combining the design styling of Rashid with the practical aspects of a handheld, cordless vacuum was not easy. Rashid designed the outer shell and delivered sketches to the engineers at TTI Floor Care, but he was not concerned about fitting everything inside the shell. Rashid, while a remarkable designer, is not accustomed to integrating engineering into his designs. In fact, the final product is fatter than the original concept in order to fit the components inside. Although the fan and motor align naturally along the axis of the device, the batteries were a bigger challenge. Handheld vacuum manufacturers are engaged in a voltage race. Even though consumers relate voltage to suction, higher voltage actually allows for increased performance and longer run times, but not necessarily both. These characteristics need to be balanced to provide optimal overall performance. The limited space inside the KURV's shell permitted only eight 1.2V sub-C sized cells. The engineers were forced to squeeze the batteries into the upper housing in a rather odd configuration of five batteries aligned with the KURV's axis surrounding the motor and three more batteries positioned above the motor, as shown in Figure 2. The integration of the charging contacts into the base unit so they are almost invisible and the use of gravity with a slight twisting action to naturally guide the KURV into its base for charging represent thoughtful engineering design that aligns beautifully with the KURV's stylish appearance.

Figure.2 The challenge in engineering the KURV was fitting the parts into the contoured body. (Images courtesy of Royal Appliance Manufacturing Company; used with permission.)

To allow easy manufacture, a clamshell body is used to trap the internal parts. But a key aspect of Rashid's design is a smooth contour—he wanted no screw bosses or parting lines. To obtain this effect, a glamour cap snaps over the clamshell. And, of course, an on-off switch would interrupt the smooth contours. The original idea was to use a capacitive touch switch, but cost and regulatory certification made this challenging. Instead engineers integrated a push-button switch into the top end of the device in a way that is obvious to the user but hidden from view, while retaining the elegant contour of the KURV. When Rashid recognized the need for exhaust vents, he specified a ring of peanut-shaped vents around the entire outer circumference of the KURV. But some vents had to be eliminated to prevent exhaust air from blowing around the debris that is to be picked up. In addition, TTI engineers had to adjust the shape of the vents and add slides to the mold to keep the vents from distorting during the molding process. In the end, though, the most controversial aspect of KURV was the color. Ideally, the colors fit with a variety of decors. In the marketplace, champagne is most popular followed by choco-latte, spice red, and harbour sky blue.

Not everyone likes the KURV. A quick scan of reviews on the Amazon or Target web sites reveals either very positive or very negative comments. One customer says "Dirt Devil KURV is the best! I love the way it looks but more, how it works" [4]. But another customer complains "Yes its very cute. And Yes, it looks good on my end table and, Yes it matches my decor.....but if that all it does I might as well bought a vase or some type of other thing that is supposed to just sit there and look pretty!! This is supposed to VACUUM!! and IT DOESN'T!!" [5]. Out of the 15 reviews on Amazon.com and Target.com at the time this was written, 10 are 4 or 5 stars and 4 are 1 or 2 stars. Only one rating was in the middle at 3 stars. This sort of love-hate dichotomy is a perfect for a niche product. It need not appeal to everyone, but some people have to love it—and buy it.

Testing of the KURV suggests that the negative reviews exaggerate the problem. And a recent issue of a Consumer Reports rates the KURV fairly well [6]. Obviously, the KURV is not intended to be a heavy-duty handheld vacuum for the wood shop or garage. Its power is lower than top of the line handheld vacuums and its small, quarter-sized suction opening (as opposed to the slot suction opening on most handheld vacuums) is small. On the other hand, the angled suction opening makes the KURV ideal for getting at the dirt in nooks and crannies. Unsophisticated testing in my home proves that it picks up little messes quite nicely. And having it located near the back door instead of down in the basement or under the kitchen sink makes it a lot more likely that someone will vacuum up that little mess right away.

Dirt Devil has carried the concept of the elegant light-duty vacuum cleaner further with four other models, all designed by Rashid [7]. The KONE, which preceded the KURV, is similar in size, but, as you might expect, is in the shape of a cone with the pointed end being the handle and the large end the base. Like the KURV, it comes in several colors designed to blend into any décor on a table, shelf, or counter. Rashid and Dirt Devil extended the concept to upright hard floor cordless vacuum cleaners. The KRUZ looks like a KURV with an extended handle and a swivel floor nozzle at the base. The BRUM looks like, well, a broom. It has bristles at the base just below a cordless vacuum unit with a long handle. The design makes it easy to suck up dirt and debris in the process of sweeping—no dust pan is needed. And the latest addition to the Dirt Devil designer series is the KWIK. A little larger than a stapler, the stylish half-moon-shaped desktop utility vacuum can be used to clean and dust desktops and computer keyboards and is charged via a computer's USB port.

Of course, Dirt Devil is reluctant to share details of the sales for their designer line of products but called the KONE a “big success” in the market with over one million sold since 2006. Dirt Devil has high expectations for the KURV and other products in the line. Interestingly, Dirt Devil had expected that having the designer name “Karim” would be a great marketing asset for the designer series of hand vacuums and prominently displays his signature on the Dirt Devil web site and product packaging. But it turned out that the designer label was not the main focus or reason for the line’s success. Markus Allemann of Dirt Devil explains, “It was more the fact that a 'real' designer was behind the product. We have found out from post-purchase research that the name Karim is not always recognized, but the main reason for purchase was the product design itself.”

Dirt Devil changed the rules of the cordless vacuum marketplace with this new line of designer vacuums. While competitors were adding options and colors, Dirt Devil and Karim Rashid created a new niche by combining smart engineering design with elegant industrial design. The idea of making cordless vacuums that customers don't need to hide away in a closet opens a whole new market. In addition to the standard Dustbuster-like cordless vacuum in the garage and basement workshop, every household now needs Dirt Devil KURV cordless vacuums in the front entry, the family room, and the dining room. Creative design invites customers to buy cordless vacuum for rooms they never would have put a cordless vacuum in before. Even the names are iconic and cute—KURV, KONE, KRUZ, BRUM, and KWIK—much better than the blasé "Extreme Power Hand Vac" or the "Cyclonic Hand Vac." The KURV and its siblings are just what Dirt Devil claims: "The New Shape of Clean" [7].

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References

- [1] Industrial Designers Society of America web site, Available at <http://www.idsa.org/absolutenm/templates/?a=851> [Accessed March 13, 2010]
- [2] Rashid web site, Available at http://www.karimrashid.com/biography_fr.html [Accessed March 13, 2010]
- [3] Royal Appliance news release, Feb. 28, 2006.
- [4] Review for KURV, Available at <http://www.amazon.com/review/R26FTUBYS6A87X> [Accessed March 13, 2010]
- [5] Review for KURV, Available at <http://www.target.com/gp/cdp/member-reviews.html?customerID=A1MK13A7617FDP> [Accessed March 13, 2010]
- [6] Quick pickup sticks and hand vacs. *Consumer Reports*, March 2009, p. 40.
- [7] Dirt Devil web site, Available at <http://www.dirtdevil.com/designerseries/intro.html> [Accessed March 13, 2010]